

THE **BIODIVERSITY**
FOOTPRINT COMPANY

Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints

Understanding data quality for decision-making

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About This Report

This report is part of the Quality Biodiversity Footprints Technical Series The focus of this working paper is on understanding ecosystem state measurement. Forthcoming papers in this series will address applying this for no net loss accounting, species accounting, and ecosystem services measurement. There is an accompanying annex to the case studies in this paper: “Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) Methodology”

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Businesses are increasingly exposed to biodiversity-related risks, regulations and disclosure requirements. These requirements are linked to Target 15 of the Global Biodiversity Framework which aims to ‘progressively reduce the negative impacts and increase the positive impacts of business on biodiversity’. This requires understanding and accurately measuring changes in the state of biodiversity. There are an increasing number of competing, and wildly different, tools and methodologies to measure ecosystem state, yet businesses are still building capacity to understand what is required. There is an urgent need for applied knowledge on ecosystem state that businesses can effectively use. This knowledge must progress through a structured pathway: i.e. from raw data to actionable information, deeper understanding, and ultimately, practical implementation.

The Biodiversity Footprint Company (TBFC) has been actively engaged in both generating and applying such knowledge in collaboration with businesses, positioning itself as a key contributor to the emerging community of practice.

The purpose of this paper is to consolidate the existing body of knowledge, identify gaps within that community, and address those gaps with the goal of enabling businesses to apply this knowledge meaningfully in support of the sustainability agenda. To that end, we:

- ▶ **Explain why ecosystem state matters to business:**

Ecosystems are a foundational pillar of biodiversity, but their degradation is accelerating. Policy responses remain insufficient, and private sector efforts are fragmented. Measuring ecosystem state offers a scalable way to track biodiversity trends, but conceptual ambiguity and methodological inconsistencies pose risks for target-setting and claims.

- ▶ **Provide an overview of challenges in ecosystem state measurement:**

There is no universally accepted definition or methodology. Key issues include terminological confusion, methodological misalignment, inadequate indicators for ecosystem complexity, unclear reference states, and risks of environmental amnesia when anthropogenic biomes are included. Ecological equivalency and spatial scale selection are critical for credible assessments.

- ▶ **Showcase our practical approach to ecosystem state measurement through a case study:**

The paper proposes a structured approach based on understanding the benefits and limitations of three main data sources: comprehensive ecosystem-specific protocols, manual classification of high-resolution imagery with or without the interpretation of site monitoring reports, and automated classification of remotely sensed data. A decision-tree guides data selection, supported by accuracy and confidence criteria covering spatial resolution, ecological equivalency, ecosystem complexity, and decision-usefulness. Transparency in assumptions and limitations is essential, as confidence levels vary significantly across data sources.

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Fagus sylvatica, European Beech. (LC)

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Global Policy & Frameworks

BBOP – Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme
GBF – Global Biodiversity Framework
KM-GBF – Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework
CBD – Convention on Biological Diversity
COP – Conference of the Parties
EIA – Environmental Impact Assessment
TNFD – Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures
GRI – Global Reporting Initiative
ICMM – International Council on Mining and Metals
IUCN – International Union for Conservation of Nature
ESRS E4 – European Sustainability Reporting Standard
IPBES – Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
SEEA EA – System of Environmental-Economic Accounting Ecosystem Accounting

Biodiversity Footprint Accounting & Assessment

BF – Biodiversity Footprint
TBF – Total Biodiversity Footprint
PBF – Positive Biodiversity Footprint
NBF – Negative Biodiversity Footprint
NNL – No Net Loss
NCA – Natural Capital Accounting
IOM – Input-Output Models
LCA – Life Cycle Assessment
MSA – Mean Species Abundance
BII – Biodiversity Intactness Index
EVI – Enhanced Vegetation Index
EBV – Essential Biodiversity Variable
MESA – Manual Ecosystem State Assessment
PES – Present Ecological State
TBFC – The Biodiversity Footprint Company
TEC – Threatened Ecological Community
EPBC Act – Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act

Data

GET – Global Ecosystem Typology (of the IUCN)
GIS – Geographic Information System
RE – Regional Ecosystem

1

WHY ECOSYSTEM STATE MATTERS TO BUSINESS?

Key messages

1. The **scale of ecosystem loss and degradation is accelerating** and deeply concerning.
2. **The global policy response remains insufficient.** International biodiversity targets have not been met.
3. **Private sector responses remain fragmented**, underregulated, and lacking in actionable disclosure.
4. The state of **ecosystems serves as a key proxy** for assessing the broader state of biodiversity. Measuring it provides a robust and scalable way for business to understand trends and set targets for biodiversity across local and global scales.
5. Yet, using ecosystem state for corporate biodiversity performance assessment is not without its challenges, namely the **lack of conceptual clarity** around definitions and measurement of ecosystem state.
6. This calls for a better understanding of ecosystem state **measurement uncertainty**, which must be explicitly considered in decision-making and disclosure processes.

1.1 The biodiversity crisis is a global policy failure

Biodiversity loss represents a fundamental threat to the functioning of Earth's life-support systems, undermining ecosystem processes on which human well-being and economic activity depend (Díaz *et al.* 2019). According to the *Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (Brondízio *et al.* 2019), human activities have significantly altered Earth's ecosystems, leading to widespread degradation and alarming integrity loss (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Indicators of global ecosystem loss from the Intergovernmental Panel of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services 2019 Assessment (adapted from Brondízio *et al.*, 2019)

To address the biodiversity crisis, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) was initiated by the UN Environment Programme in 1988. It was adopted at the 1992 Rio Earth Summit and entered into force in 1993. The CBD sets out three core goals:

- ▶ Conservation of biodiversity,
- ▶ Sustainable use of its components,
- ▶ Fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of genetic resources.

CBD decisions often result in the development of protocols, guidelines, and / or voluntary measures for member countries (Parties to the Convention), which can choose whether to adopt and translate them into national policies and laws. These have often direct impacts on business (e.g. permitting requirements).

However, progress on the targets adopted at the CBD's conferences of the parties (COPs) in 2010 (Aichi Biodiversity Targets) has been limited. According to the Global Biodiversity Outlook 5 (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity 2020): *"At the global level, none of the 20 targets have been fully achieved, though six have been partially achieved (Targets 9, 11, 16, 17, 19, and 20). Of the 60 individual elements that comprise the Aichi Targets, seven have been achieved, 38 show progress, 13 show no progress or regression, and two remain of unknown status"*. Moreover, implementation gaps, especially within the private sector, remain a serious concern (Díaz *et al.* 2019).

The 2022 Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) (CBD 2023), intended as a post-2020 successor to the Aichi Targets, faces similar scepticism. *"There is little clarity on how to operationalize biodiversity goals across industries and financial institutions"* (Bedford *et al.* 2024). Without clearer mechanisms for sector-wide implementation, many fear that the KM-GBF may not yield better results (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity 2020; Zhu *et al.* 2024). Although certain positive developments have emerged - for instance, well-managed protected area systems in several countries (Geldmann *et al.* 2015; Li *et al.* 2024) and some threatened species showing signs of recovery (Simkins *et al.* 2025; Young *et al.* 2025) – overall biodiversity loss continues unabated, with no clear indication of biodiversity mainstreaming in the private sector. While the CBD's intent may be clear, more determination, effective action, funding, monitoring, and mainstreaming are urgently needed.

1.2 Addressing the biodiversity crisis is an imperative for business

Efforts to mainstream biodiversity in the private sector currently rely on both regulatory compliance and voluntary initiatives. Both types of approaches have significant limitations in ensuring meaningful ecosystem protection, as summarized below.

1.2.1 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) legislation and the Mitigation Hierarchy

At the national level, many governments enforce Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) legislation, typically structured around the mitigation hierarchy: avoid, minimize, restore, and offset. However, implementation varies widely across jurisdictions, resulting in inconsistent standards (Bezombes *et al.* 2017):

- ▶ Scope discrepancies: Definitions of what ecosystems or economic activities fall under EIA vary significantly. Besides, the regulatory mandate is often lacking to look at impacts on ecosystems (i.e. focus on threatened species).
- ▶ Diverse indicators and metrics: There is no universal agreement on which ecosystem indicators or metrics to use.
- ▶ Ecological equivalency challenges: Offset rules differ in how losses and gains are calculated or exchanged.
- ▶ Offset design: Offset ratios, additionality criteria, and monitoring requirements are often vague or weakly enforced.

This heterogeneity undermines the comparability, accountability, and credibility of impact mitigation strategies across borders.

1.2.2 Voluntary corporate biodiversity initiatives and disclosures

The private sector is under growing pressure to use robust ecosystem state data to assess their baseline impacts, set targets and monitor progress towards them beyond what is required by law (e.g., ICM, 2024). This demand is driven by the GBF, notably in the context of Target 15 (see Box 1), and a range of corporate disclosure mechanisms, including the *GRI 101: Biodiversity 2024 Topic Standard*, *Taskforce for Nature-related Financial Disclosures - TNFD* as well as regulatory requirements such as the draft *ESRS E4: Biodiversity and Ecosystems*.

Yet there is little evidence of quantitative biodiversity disclosures. Despite this, several businesses have adopted voluntary, non-standardized biodiversity policies and disclosure practices (Baboukardos *et al.* 2024; Bedford *et al.* 2024; Elliot *et al.* 2024). While it signals growing awareness, these reporting approaches suffer from several shortcomings:

- ▶ Lack of standardization: Companies choose their own metrics, boundaries, and reporting formats, leading to inconsistent disclosures.
- ▶ Low disclosure quality: Most biodiversity-related disclosures are qualitative, emphasizing management narratives over measurable performance.
- ▶ Limited risk insight: Current reporting rarely provides decision-useful information on biodiversity-related business risks or dependencies.

1.3 Ecosystem state is a proxy for tracking biodiversity trends

Box 1. Target 15 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

KM-GBF Target 15 requires that governments ‘Take legal, administrative or policy measures to encourage and enable business, and in particular to ensure that large and transnational companies and financial institutions: (a) Regularly monitor, assess, and transparently disclose their risks, dependencies and impacts on biodiversity, including with requirements for all large as well as transnational companies and financial institutions along their operations, supply and value chains and portfolios;...’

How can businesses regularly monitor, assess, and transparently disclose their risks, dependencies and impacts on biodiversity in a standardised and comparable way? As defined by the CBD, biodiversity is: “*The variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.*” (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2011).

The degradation of ecosystems is often presented as the best indicator by which to quantify business impacts on biodiversity as a whole (Bedford *et al.* 2025; Nicholson *et al.* 2021). Ecosystems are defined as “*dynamic complexes of plant, animal, and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment, interacting as a functional unit*” (Brondízio *et al.* 2019). While businesses and policymakers cannot feasibly track the state of all species, measuring the state of ecosystems provides a robust and scalable way to understand trends in biodiversity across local and global scales. Understanding what or what isn’t an ecosystem, and how to measure impacts on them, as a proxy for the broader state of biodiversity, has thus never been more relevant.

Accurately describing the state of ecosystems has become one of the most pressing challenges in biodiversity science and policy. Governments, businesses, and conservation actors increasingly rely on ecosystem state data to meet the requirements of the growing number of mandatory and voluntary corporate disclosure frameworks (Bedford *et al.* 2023). When integrated with corporate biodiversity accounting (Houdet 2024; Houdet *et al.* 2020; Houdet & Teren 2022), ecosystem state data enables the generation of biodiversity footprint (BF) information, across multiple scales, supporting baseline assessments, target-setting, mitigation hierarchy-based action planning, performance monitoring and auditable stakeholder reporting.

Yet, using ecosystem state to reverse trends in the biodiversity crisis is not without its challenges. The lack of conceptual clarity around the definition of ecosystem state and how it should be measured can hamper meaningful progress. This is of particular concern in the context of emerging:

- ▶ Corporate biodiversity targets and / or claims (De Silva *et al.* 2019; Rainey *et al.* 2015), typically framed as no net loss (NNL), net gain, zero harm or nature positive.

- ▶ Biodiversity credit trading (Manez & Clifton 2025; The Taskforce on Nature Markets 2023; World Economic Forum 2024), which are seen as complementary to compliance-driven markets (Hanley & Simpson 2025; Needham *et al.* 2019).

Inadequate ecosystem typologies, unfit-for-purpose state data or shifting baselines can all contribute to biased decision-making and / or even unsubstantiated or misleading claims. This calls for a better understanding of ecosystem state measurement uncertainty, which must be explicitly considered in decision-making and disclosure processes.

1.4 Measuring business impacts on ecosystem state

Before addressing the challenges of measuring ecosystem state, it is essential to clarify its intrinsic link to ecosystem impact assessment. Ecosystem impacts represent the positive or negative changes in an ecosystem caused by external forces. These forces may arise from natural disturbances - such as wildfires or floods - or from human activities, including land-use change, pollution, resource extraction, and successful rehabilitation. In short, ecosystem impacts are simply changes in ecosystem state, whether positive or negative (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Conceptual diagram showing shifts in ecosystem state can occur both positively and negatively, and as a result of human activities and/or natural drivers.

There are broadly two different approaches to measuring ecosystem state change. While some methods measure impact drivers (Box 2) to estimate or model changes in ecosystem state, others directly measure changes in ecosystem state (see Section 2.3).

Measuring an impact driver involves, for instance, the measurement of greenhouse gas emissions or the surface area of a land use which are then used as input data to assess ecosystem impacts. On the other hand, directly measuring an impact involves measuring changes in ecosystem-related variables (see Section 2.4). This distinction has major implications for accuracy (see Section 3.5). The focus of this paper is on directly measuring impacts for higher accuracy and reliability.

Moreover, impacts by business can be direct or indirect, and should not be confused with direct / indirect drivers of changes (Box 2). This distinction is important when considering responsibility over changes in state of ecosystems. Direct impacts occur when specific actions (impact drivers) - such as land clearing or ecosystem restoration - result in observable changes to biodiversity (Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020). These changes are traceable to identifiable biodiversity features and may be:

- ▶ Short-term or long-term,
- ▶ Recurrent (e.g. seasonal operations),
- ▶ Permanent (e.g. infrastructure development like buildings or car parks).

Such impacts fall within a company's operational control (e.g. direct operations within the value chain) and are typically verifiable through field data or monitoring.

Indirect impacts cannot be directly linked to a specific business activity. They result from broader drivers (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions, cumulative water pollution), multiple business activities and sometimes require modelling tools to estimate the changes in biodiversity state (Schipper *et al.* 2020). These impacts emerge from diffuse interactions across social, environmental, and economic systems, often beyond a company's legal or operational boundaries. Measuring a partial set of impact drivers may thus not be sufficient to provide an accurate assessment of ecosystem state.

Both direct and indirect impacts can occur across the whole value chain (Endangered Wildlife Trust, 2020):

- ▶ Direct operations (gate-to-gate), which cover activities over which a business holds ownership or control,
- ▶ Upstream (cradle-to-gate), which covers the activities of suppliers,
- ▶ Downstream (gate-to-grave), which covers activities linked to the purchase, use, re-use, recovery, recycling, and final disposal of a business' products and services.

Box 2: Defining impact drivers

There are two overarching categories of drivers contributing to the ongoing impacts on ecosystems: direct and indirect drivers of change in their state (Brondízio et al., 2019). Indirect drivers form the broader context in which direct pressures emerge and evolve. Anthropogenic direct drivers are particularly shaped by these systemic structures and decision-making processes. Both public sector entities (e.g., state-owned utilities, military departments) and private sector actors (e.g., agriculture, mining, finance) exert a profound influence on direct drivers. Simultaneously, societal norms, organisations and individual / collective behaviours drive the evolution of indirect pressures.

Direct drivers of change ("Pressures")

These are biophysical or anthropogenic forces that unequivocally affect biodiversity and ecosystem processes. They tend to operate at a proximate level and often interact synergistically with one another, sometimes feeding back into indirect drivers. Key examples include:

- ▶ Land-use change (e.g., deforestation, agricultural expansion).
- ▶ Climate change.
- ▶ Pollution (air, water, and soil contaminants).
- ▶ Exploitation of natural resources (e.g., overfishing, logging).
- ▶ Invasive alien species.

These drivers are frequently the result of both natural processes and human activities and are often shaped by larger systemic influences. Measuring these drivers of change can only provide an indirect estimation of the state of ecosystems.

Indirect Drivers of Change ("Underlying Causes")

Indirect drivers operate more diffusely, influencing both direct drivers and other indirect drivers. They are socio-economic, cultural, and institutional in nature and include:

- ▶ Government policies (e.g., trade, subsidies, fiscal strategies).
- ▶ Cultural value shifts and behavioural norms.
- ▶ Technological innovation and diffusion.
- ▶ Voluntary corporate policies and financial sector decisions.

Interactions of drivers and changes in ecosystem state

Direct and indirect drivers often interact within specific geographic contexts, reinforcing or counteracting one another. As a result, ecosystem state reflects the combined, layered impacts of multiple drivers (Figure 2). This interplay introduces methodological challenges when assessing ecosystem state based on impact-driver data alone – i.e. risks of double-counting (Houdet and Teren, 2022).

Irrespective of the type of impact and impact driver, this paper focuses on ecosystem state measurement. As per the BD Protocol, we measure impacts on ecosystems as changes in their state, with the link to biodiversity footprints explained in **Figure 3**.

As per the BD Protocol (Endangered Wildlife Trust, 2020), Biodiversity Footprints are assessed through three KPIs: TBF, NBF and PBF, explained in this image. These equations apply to all polygons of uniform state scores within an assessment boundary, enabling the consolidation of results across sites, operations, regions or countries.

Figure 3. The three key Biodiversity Footprint Indicators

Any private-sector biodiversity initiative - whether voluntary or regulatory, addressing direct and / or indirect impacts, and applied at any point along the value chain - must confront a common set of foundational questions. Each represents a “wicked problem”: conceptually complex, value-laden, and resistant to simple solutions, yet tractable through explicit methodological choices.

Leucospermum patersonii, Silveredge pincushion. (NT)

2

ECOSYSTEM STATE MEASUREMENT CHALLENGES

Key messages

1. There is **no universally accepted definition or methodology** for ecosystem state measurement, creating ambiguity that undermines both regulatory compliance and voluntary biodiversity initiatives.
2. Different biodiversity footprint methodologies tackle ecosystem state assessment in different ways. While some methods measure **impact drivers** to estimate or model changes in ecosystem state, **others directly measure changes in ecosystem state**. The focus of this paper is on measuring the latter.
3. **Measurement approaches differ significantly**: Pressure-based methods provide broad-scale, theoretical estimates. Natural Capital Accounting (NCA) offers location-specific, time-sensitive tracking of actual ecosystem state changes, making it more suitable for biodiversity footprint accounting.
4. **Terminological clarity is essential**: Terms like condition, state, integrity, and quality are used interchangeably, causing inconsistency.
5. Ecosystem condition is widely accepted as the most appropriate term for corporate biodiversity assessments; this paper uses ecosystem state as the neutral option.
6. **No single indicator captures ecosystem complexity**: Effective assessment requires integrating compositional, structural, and functional attributes rather than relying on one-dimensional proxies.
7. **Anthropogenic ecosystems should be excluded** from biodiversity footprinting to avoid masking historical losses (environmental amnesia) and prevent “shifting baselines”.
8. **Ecological equivalency must be applied at an appropriate spatial scale**: Coarse typologies distort ecological reality and can mislead corporate biodiversity targets.
9. **Reference state selection is critical**: Historical baselines are often impractical, while contemporary benchmarks risk overestimating ecosystem health. Transparency in assumptions and limitations is essential to avoid bias and maintain credibility.
10. Overall, companies should prioritize approaches which **clearly document assumptions and limitations** to ensure ecological validity, fitness-for-purpose and decision-usefulness.

2.1 Choosing the right terminology

Multiple definitions and frameworks have been developed to conceptualize ecosystem state, each shaped by distinct historical and epistemological influences. **Table 1** highlights the range of terminology and concepts employed across different contexts. These are frequently used interchangeably in the context of corporate biodiversity footprint assessments. Among these, *ecosystem condition* is widely used in corporate biodiversity assessments (Bedford *et al.* 2023).

Table 1. The multiple ways of conceptualising ecosystem state

Term	Some examples
Ecosystem condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Keith <i>et al.</i> (2020) offer a conceptual framework for condition accounts. ▶ United Nations <i>et al.</i> (2021) define it as the quality of an ecosystem measured by its abiotic and biotic characteristics. ▶ Czúcz <i>et al.</i> (2021) propose a typology for ecosystem condition variables.
Ecosystem health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Lu <i>et al.</i> (2015) discuss health in relation to sustainability and resilience. ▶ Giraudoux (2022) provides a formal definition linking health to diversity, resilience, and functioning. ▶ The Encyclopaedia of Life Support Systems (EOLSS) (Rapport <i>et al.</i>, no date) frames health using vigour, organization, and resilience.
Ecosystem integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Keith <i>et al.</i> (2013) introduce integrity in the context of ecosystem collapse risk. ▶ CBD SBSTTA (2021) links integrity with dominant ecological characteristics within their natural ranges of variation which can withstand and recover from most perturbations. ▶ Hansen <i>et al.</i> (2021) link integrity to structure, function, and composition.
Ecosystem status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Wu <i>et al.</i> (2022) propose a framework for evaluating ecosystem quality and status using reference conditions and key indicators. ▶ Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2024) use ecosystem status assessment to identify important zones for ecological protection and restoration.
Ecosystem quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Woods <i>et al.</i> (2018) discuss harmonization of ecosystem quality indicators in life cycle impact assessment. ▶ Sturbois <i>et al.</i> (2023) present a framework for assessing ecological quality using fuzzy logic and trajectory analysis. ▶ Klein (2024) links habitat quality to ecosystem functioning and resilience.
Ecosystem state	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Capon <i>et al.</i> (2015) critically examine state definitions rooted in alternative stable state theory in freshwater systems - emphasizing empirical evidence, thresholds, and the persistence of states. ▶ Stringham, Krueger and Shaver (2003) present State-and-Transition Models where ecosystem state is a discrete configuration characterized by distinct species assemblages and ecosystem functions, with clearly defined transitions and thresholds ▶ Meng, Fang and Scavia (2021) apply theoretical constructs of ecosystem state in practice, comparing traditional indices with stability and regime-shift theory.

In this paper we adopt the term ecosystem state as the most neutral option. Unlike terms such as *health* or *quality*, ecosystem state does not imply normative judgement, ideal functionality, or human utility. For example, the term ‘ecosystem health’ misrepresents ecology as an organisms and has led to problematic indices of health (Suter II 1993).

Ecosystem state simply describes where an ecosystem stands, at a given place and time, against its reference situation (unpacked in Section 2.6). The metrics to assess state therefore need to recognise this (unpacked in Section 2.4).

2.2 Ecosystem typologies

Humans have dramatically reshaped global biodiversity and ecosystem processes, leaving a profound imprint on the natural world. This has relevance for how we define ecosystems.

In developing the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology (GET), the authors found that, out of 23 existing global ecosystem classifications, very few integrated anthropogenic ecosystems (Keith *et al.* 2022). Yet, anthropogenic influences create challenges as they may modify the very defining features of ecosystems to the extent of complete transformation. To overcome these challenges, the GET distinguishes Anthropogenic systems where humans have created and sustained ecosystems, from measurements of ecosystem state that ‘reflect divergence from reference states arising from human activity’ (Keith *et al.* 2022). This has resulted in an entirely new terrestrial biome (the intensive land-use system, T7 - **Box 3**), and several anthropogenic and artificial aquatic systems.

Recognising and measuring the state of anthropogenic systems such as annual croplands, plantations and pastures, urban systems, subterranean canals or artificial shores has direct relevance to measuring ecosystem services and dis-services (Costanza *et al.* 2017; Guo *et al.* 2022; Gutierrez-Arellano & Mulligan 2018; Larson *et al.* 2019; Mitchell *et al.* 2024; Saunders 2020; Wang *et al.* 2022). The supply of ecosystem services can serve as the desired states of anthropogenic systems against which progress can be measured or modelled. Changes in land use act as a key determining factor in this process (Bai *et al.* 2025; Eigenbrod *et al.* 2010; Zhang *et al.* 2022).

From this perspective, optimal ecosystem state is typically determined considering competing interests and trade-offs with respect to the supply of various ecosystem services. Land use choices typically oppose provisioning services (e.g. wood, crops, fish) with regulation (e.g. erosion, nutrient cycling and pollination control) or cultural (e.g. education, scenic beauty, symbolic interactions) services. For instance, changing agricultural practices (e.g. crop rotation, tillage practices, grazing systems, fertilizer management) will affect the supply of different categories of ecosystem services (Cozim-Melges *et al.* 2024; Morizet-Davis *et al.* 2023). Rewilding projects involving farming enterprises, such as the Knepp Wildland Project, show the breadth of potential optimal states a single land use might have (Cary & Wartmann 2025; Dempsey 2021; Underwood *et al.* 2021).

Box 3. The definition of ‘The Anthrome’ in the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology 2.0 (D. A. Keith *et al.*, 2020).

The anthrome or intensive land-use biome

Intensive land-use systems include major anthropogenic enterprises of cropping, pastoralism, plantation farming, and urbanisation. Human intervention is a dominating influence on this biome, also known as the ‘anthrome’. Maintenance of these systems is contingent on continuing human interventions, including alterations to the physical structure of vegetation and substrates (e.g. clearing, earthworks and drainage), the supplementation of resources (e.g. with irrigation and fertilisers) and the introduction and control of biota. These interventions maintain disequilibrium community structure and composition, low endemism and low functional and taxonomic diversity. Target biota are genetically manipulated (by selective breeding or molecular engineering) to promote rapid growth rates, efficient resource capture, enhanced resource allocation to production tissues, and tolerance to harsh environmental conditions, predators and diseases. Non-target biota include widely dispersed, cosmopolitan opportunists with short lifecycles. Many intensive land use systems are maintained as artificial mosaics of contrasting patch types at scales of metres to hundreds of metres.

The delivery of a specified set of ecosystem services - quantified in terms of their quantity, quality, and/or temporal attributes - forms the basis for selecting ecosystem types and informs the methodology used to assess ecosystem state. Consequently, the reference ecosystem state (i.e. the selected or intended target attributes) is shaped by anthropogenic decision-making processes. These decisions vary according to stakeholder context: for individual landowners, choices may be guided by personal preferences, regulatory frameworks, or external advisory inputs; for corporate entities, ecosystem service targets are typically influenced by internal management policies and shareholder priorities; and at the industry level, reference states may be aligned with sector-specific production standards or certification schemes.

While anthropogenic ecosystems provide a useful framework for analysing and managing human-modified landscapes in accordance with varying stakeholder objectives, they are not appropriate for biodiversity footprint accounting (Houdet & Teren 2022). This approach necessitates the quantification of total biodiversity impacts, specifically with reference to ecosystem typologies grounded in conservation science: i.e. biodiversity footprinting is concerned with the intrinsic values (Loreau 2014) of biodiversity. To include anthropogenic systems, or misinterpret reference states (see section 2.6) is at the risk of invoking the ‘Shifting Baseline Syndrome’ (Soga & Gaston 2018).

Accordingly, the use of anthropogenic biomes in biodiversity footprinting introduces the risk of *environmental amnesia*, whereby the historical loss and degradation of non-anthropogenic ecosystems is obscured. Environmental amnesia refers to the phenomenon whereby each generation perceives the environmental conditions of its formative years as normative, thereby overlooking long-term ecological

degradation (Kahn & Weiss 2017; Matsler *et al.* 2021; Trouwborst 2021; Walshe *et al.* 2025). This cognitive bias contributes to a diminished awareness of historical ecosystem states, masking the full scope of transformation that has occurred throughout the Anthropocene, especially since the start of the industrial revolution.

Companies may assume that what they see now is both ‘natural’ and a desired state for biodiversity. Consequently, adopting ecosystem typologies that incorporate anthropogenic systems - such as annual croplands, sown pastures, plantations, urban zones, or industrial landscapes (Keith *et al.*, 2020) - leads to shifting baselines in biodiversity-related decision-making, planning and target-setting (Houdet & Teren 2022; Pierrel 2022; Rapworth *et al.* 2009).

Besides, redefining ecosystem boundaries based on current structural, functional, or compositional attributes undermines the establishment of a standardized ecosystem state measurement framework for biodiversity conservation target-setting. State assessment - ranging from reference state to fully degraded - would be contingent on assessor or client preferences regarding desired land uses at the time of evaluation, thereby impeding result aggregation and cross-comparison across ecosystems, regions, land uses, industries, or nations. For instance, the reference state of an industrial, urban garden or agricultural ecosystem differs fundamentally from that of the non-anthropogenic wetland, grassland or forest it has replaced, either recently or centuries prior. Those measurements cannot be compared to one another, as they do not share the same measurement scale and respond to diametrically opposed objectives: i.e. utilitarian ecosystem services supply versus intrinsic biodiversity conservation (see example in Box 4).

Box 4. Part 1:

A case-study comparison of using anthropogenic system (**Table B**) versus non-anthropogenic ecosystem (**Table A**) typologies when measuring changes in ecosystem state

Loss masking:

Anthropogenic classification systems obscure the disappearance of non-anthropogenic ecosystems once they are converted. For example, “unused Borneo peat swamp forests” vanish from the records and are reassigned to anthropogenic categories. This practice fosters environmental amnesia and prevents accurate measurement of total ecosystem state loss.

Scale inconsistency:

Table B has state assessment scales that are ground on different conceptual foundations. Anthropogenic system state assessment emphasizes management practices / effectiveness towards targets (e.g. a scale ranging from a minimum of 0 for poor management practices to a maximum of 3 corresponding to certified management practices), whereas non-anthropogenic ecosystem state assessment measures deviation from a “natural” reference state. Consequently, reported net changes since 1990 differ significantly: **-750 ha eq. lost** under the non-anthropogenic classification versus **-483.33 ha eq. lost** under the anthropogenic classification. We thus argue that using anthropogenic ecosystem classification for biodiversity footprint assessments is inappropriate. It hides historical ecosystem losses and enables the constant shifting of baselines to satisfy changing stakeholder needs.

Box 4 Part 2. A case-study comparison of using anthropogenic system (Table B) versus non-anthropogenic ecosystem (Table A) typologies

			TBF	PBF	TBF	PBF	TBF	PBF	TBF	Net	PBF	Net
			(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha)	change	(ha)	change
			(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha)	(ha)	(ha eq.)	(ha eq.)

Table A: Non-anthropogenic ecosystem classification

Categories	Land use	Ecosystem state (Ref = 6)	1990 baseline		2020		2025		1990-2025	
Borneo peat swamp forests	None	6	1000	1000	400	400	0	0	-1000	-1000
Borneo peat swamp forests	Forestry	3	0	0	200	100	500	250	500	250
Borneo peat swamp forests	Monocultures (palm oil, pastures)	0	0	0	400	0	500	0	500	0
		Total	1000	1000	1000	500	1000	250	0	-750

Table B: Anthropogenic system classification

Categories	Land use	Condition score (Ref =6)	1990 baseline		2020		2025		1990-2025	
Unused Borneo peat swamp forests	Unused Borneo peat swamp forests	6	1000	1000	400	400	0	0	-1000	-1000
Production forest	Production forest (certified)	3	0	0	100	100	200	200	200	200
Production forest	Production (poorly managed)	0	0	0	100	0	300	0	300	0
Palm oil farm	Palm oil farm (certified)	3	0	0	100	100	150	150	150	150
Palm oil farm	Palm oil farm (certified - problems to address)	2	0	0	100	66.66	100	66.66	100	66.66
Pastures	Pastures (certified)	3	0	0	100	100	100	100	100	100
Pastures	Pastures (poorly managed)	0	0	0	100	0	150	0	150	0
		Total	1000	1000	1000	766.66	1000	516.66	-150	-483.33

Some may counterargue that emerging or novel ecosystems (Box 5) are becoming the norm, resulting from biotic changes (e.g. species extinction or invasion), abiotic changes (e.g. land use or climate shifts), or a combination thereof (Hobbs, Higgs and Harris, 2009). These ecosystems should be identified and managed as such, acknowledging the blurred distinctions between human and natural systems, the irreversibility of some changes (e.g. extinctions), the challenge of goal-setting amid diverse priorities, and the importance of inclusive restoration practices (Macdonald & King 2018).

Box 5. The definition of 'A novel ecosystem (Hobbs, Higgs and Hall, 2013)

A novel ecosystem is a system of abiotic, biotic and social components (and their interactions) that, by virtue of human influence, differ from those that prevailed historically, having a tendency to self-organize, and manifest novel qualities without intensive human management.”

While this can be a powerful argument, it is also critical (a) to distinguish novel ecosystems from anthropogenic systems (which require intensive human management) and (b) to recognize what is deemed novel today may be transient. Technological advancements - such as large-scale eradication of exotic species - have demonstrated the potential to restore severely altered island (Graham *et al.* 2024; Kurle *et al.* 2021; Springer 2018) and mainland ecosystems (Finlayson *et al.* 2022; Heurick 2010; Moseby *et al.* 2025).

Many degraded ecosystems were previously treated as novel (e.g. islands invaded by exotic species), before any commitments and action to reverse trends (Ewel *et al.* 2013). Because human intervention can serve as a positive force in improving ecosystem state, including novel ecosystems into ecosystem typologies should follow clear guidelines around satisfying criteria, such as evidence of self-organization, and novel qualities without intensive human management. The prohibitive costs of ecosystem restoration (Reside *et al.* 2024) or lack of social / political support should not be deciding factor in this process.

2.3 Measurement approaches

There are three broad, and somewhat complementary, common approaches for collecting data to evaluate ecosystem states (Bedford *et al.* 2022):

- ▶ Primary ecosystem state data: Collected directly *in situ* for the specific purpose of the assessment, this includes on-the-ground ecological surveys (e.g. vegetation surveys, community sampling, and bioacoustics monitoring).
- ▶ Secondary ecosystem state data: They include geospatial data layers that can be overlaid with business activity location data and may originate from various sources, including ecological models or remote sensing technologies. Spatial layers tracking changes in ecosystem extent and state, including indicators of fragmentation and connectivity, provide insight into broader ecological transformations.
- ▶ Modelled pressure-state data: Model-based assessments estimate biodiversity change by quantifying the effects of specific pressures. These models establish ‘pressure-state’ relationships, often calibrated using global datasets. Results can be downscaled to assess localized ecosystem impacts of company activities while accuracy improves when primary pressure data is used instead of proxies or sectoral averages.

Moreover, there are three main methodological approaches that produce Biodiversity Footprints (BF) and make use of ecosystem state data: Input-Outputs Models (IOM), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Natural Capital Accounting (NCA). NCA approaches are conceptually very different from IOM and LCA approaches. On the one hand, BF estimations from IOM and LCA approaches are based on impact driver or pressure (see Section 2.3 and Box 2) data - such as product volume or mass, GHG emissions, and land use - sourced from company-specific inputs or industry averages, using various scientific studies and global databases. Different tools would use different metrics and “end-point” multipliers (Bromwich *et al.* 2025; Damiani *et al.* 2023; Marques *et al.* 2017). On the other hand, NCA approaches apply accounting rules to organise primary and secondary ecosystem state data to produce BF (Houdet 2024; Houdet *et al.* 2020; United Nations *et al.* 2021).

While there is no single approach to ecosystem state measurement, there are key criteria that help identify the most appropriate method for the intended purpose(s) as shown in **Table 2** (adapted from Bedford *et al.*, 2022):

- ▶ The spatial precision of state measurement: NCA utilizes location-specific ecosystem state data, whereas LCA and IOM approaches estimate ecosystem impacts applicable to broader ecoregions or countries.
- ▶ The accuracy of measurement: NCA utilizes location-specific ecosystem state data of varying accuracy (see Section 2.3), whereas LCA and IOM approaches estimate potential impacts on ecosystems, either reflecting unverified on the ground changes or mere theoretical impacts.
- ▶ The responsiveness of measurement to mitigation measures: with NCA, results will respond to mitigation measures depending on the activity and ecosystem type (e.g. restoration may take many years to achieve desired goals in a tropical forest) whereas LCA and IOM approaches may see BF results react to broad level reductions in pressures / impact drivers.
- ▶ The feasibility to apply at scale: Because IOM and LCA approaches do not require location data, they may be replicated quickly and rapidly. Depending on whether *in situ* data is used, NCA can also be applied at scale; which has implications for the accuracy of the assessed ecosystem state (see Section 3.5).

In other words, IOM and LCA methods produce time-bound / snapshot results which do not show impacts on actual ecosystems. IOM approaches are useful to identify risks and high impact areas for industries or large organisations while LCA approaches are designed to identify risks and high impact areas for products and supply chains (i.e. heatmap of impact drivers contributing the most to the BF). On the other hand, NCA approaches are designed to track changes in the state of actual ecosystems (spatial representation with GIS coordinates), both from one period to another and cumulatively over time (Houdet *et al.* 2020).

Table 2. Four characteristics to consider when determining methodology for ecosystem state measurement (adapted from Bedford *et al.* 2022)

Methodology characteristics	Definition	‘High’ level of characteristic	‘Medium’ level of characteristic	‘Low’ level of characteristic
Spatial precision of state measurement	Refers to whether the resulting measure considers the geographic location of the activity and the biodiversity within the area.	State at specific location measured.	Biodiversity state across wider area than specific location represented (e.g. ecoregion).	State measure has no spatial specificity (e.g. results are globally applicable).
Accuracy of measurement	Refers to how well the measurement reflects changes that are actually occurring ‘on the ground’.	Measure estimates actual state change ‘on the ground’.	Reflects on-the-ground changes but changes are not ground-truthed.	Estimates state-change based on pressures.
Responsiveness of measurement to mitigation	Refers to whether the approach produces a metric that can change over time in response to changes in company management interventions.	Metric responds to site-level mitigation interventions at the appropriate temporal scale.	Metric responds to broad-level reductions in pressure (e.g. reduced land intensity).	‘Snap-shot’ metric that does not reflect company management interventions but may change based on avoidance of areas.
Feasibility to apply at scale	Refers to the relative feasibility of applying the approach over A) multiple sites within an organisation or B) across value chains or C) across portfolios of companies.	Able to be replicated across business activities rapidly and does not necessarily require location data.	Able to be applied rapidly at scale but requires location data.	Involves in-situ data collection so often unfeasible to apply at scale.

2.4 Measuring ecosystem complexity

Biodiversity is complex and biodiversity science has long recognised this multidimensionality. Noss (1990) conceptualised biodiversity as comprising three core attributes - composition, structure, and function - each of which can be expressed at multiple hierarchical levels, from genes and species to communities, ecosystems, and landscapes. For example, compositional attributes range from genetic diversity within populations to the distribution of ecosystem types across regions; structural attributes span vegetation layers, habitat configuration, and landscape pattern; and functional attributes include processes such as productivity, disturbance regimes, hydrological dynamics, and species interactions operating across scales.

The concept of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) was later introduced to advance the collection, sharing, and use of biodiversity information collected through different methods such as *in situ* monitoring or remote sensing (Navarro *et al.* 2017; Pereira *et al.* 2013), clearly distinguishing ecosystem and species variables (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Framework of the six classes of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) grouped by species-focused and ecosystem-focused approaches (from Fernández *et al.* (2020))

When measuring ecosystem state, the focus is primarily on the last three EBV classes - ecosystem composition, functioning, and structure variables (Figure 4) - in comparison to their reference states (see Section 2.6). However, methods for assessing ecosystem state vary in terms of which indicators they employ. Some operate globally, while others are tailored to specific ecosystem types. Each method utilizes one or more indicators to evaluate and monitor ecosystem state, meaning that while none provides a fully exhaustive picture, all serve as proxies for the overall state of ecosystems (Table 3).

Biodiversity footprints from input-output models (IOM) or life-cycle assessment (LCA) focus on compositional variables, such as Mean Species Abundance (MSA) (Alkemade *et al.* 2009; De Weert *et al.* 2025) or Potentially Disappeared Fraction of Species (PDF) (Goedkoop *et al.* 2022; Stranddorf *et al.* 2023).

On the other hand, site-based or ecosystem-specific ecosystem state measurement methods may use a broader variety of indicators. For instance, BioCondition, widely applied in Queensland, Australia for terrestrial ecosystem condition assessments, integrates both compositional and structural vegetation attributes to determine ecosystem condition (Eyre. *et al.* 2015). WET-Health, a widely applied freshwater ecosystem state assessment methodology in Southern Africa, is largely focused on structural and functional indicators related to hydrology, geomorphology and water quality, with limited compositional variables (Macfarlane *et al.* 2020).

Table 3. Comparative analysis of variables used in a selection ecosystem state metrics, Mean Species Abundance (MSA), WET-Health and BioCondition

	Mean Species Abundance (MSA)	WET-Health	BioCondition
Composition variable(s)	Species abundance / richness, expressed as a ratio of actual number of species compared to reference abundance	Presence / absence of key wetland plants, exotic species density / cover	Native plant / tree / grass species richness, non-native plant cover
Functional variable(s)	None	Water input (quantity, flood peaks, seasonality), sediment inputs, distribution and retention	None
Structural variable(s)	None	Water retention and distribution (e.g. stream channel modification), geomorphic structure (depth and distribution of sediment deposits), etc.	Large trees, tree canopy height / cover, coarse woody debris, shrub cover, size of patch, connectivity, etc.
Description	Global model of biodiversity intactness as a function of multiple anthropogenic pressures on the environment. Single aggregate compositional metric derived from multiple pressures.	Single Present Ecological State (PES) aggregate metric of wetland state is assessed by scoring the perceived deviation from a theoretical reference condition of various compositional, functional and structural metrics, where the reference condition is defined as the un-impacted condition in which ecosystems show little or no influence of human actions.	A condition assessment framework for Queensland that provides a measure of how well a terrestrial ecosystem is functioning for biodiversity values. Numeric score shows the degree to which the attributes of a patch of vegetation differ from the attributes of the same vegetation in its reference state.
Key resources	(Schipper <i>et al.</i> 2020)	(Macfarlane <i>et al.</i> 2020)	(Eyre. <i>et al.</i> 2015)

2.5 Ecological equivalency

Ecological equivalency is the cornerstone of environmental impact assessment and the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy (Bergès *et al.* 2020; Boileau *et al.* 2022; Borges-Matos *et al.* 2025). Ecologically equivalent ecosystem gains and losses are key to understanding the net outcomes of projects. In a No-Net-loss (NNL) policy or compliance context (e.g. projects subject to authorization procedures), approaches for assessing ecological equivalence may consider ecological, spatial, temporal, and uncertainty dimensions (Bezombes *et al.* 2017). Responses to these challenges vary across jurisdictions, often reflected in different offset ratios, permanence criteria, or additionality requirements. Such differences are shaped by local stakeholder dynamics, as well as by distinct political and decision-making contexts.

From the perspective of corporate biodiversity footprint assessments, ecological equivalency has not yet become a standardised, core component for methodology development, data selection or implementation (Bedford *et al.* 2022, 2023; Houdet *et al.* 2020). This can lead to conflict between measurement approaches between compliance and voluntary initiatives. Where it is part of the ecosystem state measurement process, the key factor considered is often the choice of spatial scale for ecosystem identification and delineation. This typically depends on the availability of classification typologies (Keith *et al.*, 2022) and the associated maps of historical ecosystem extent. From this perspective, additional challenges should be mentioned:

- ▶ Identifying and mapping ecotones, as well as
- ▶ Providing evidence of ecosystem type change (e.g. emergence of novel properties), for instance due to external forces (e.g. climate change).

Assuming the selected biodiversity footprint methodology measures impacts on actual ecosystems (i.e. extent of ecosystems delineated in a GIS), the selection of an appropriate ecosystem typology is the first element that directly shapes the results of an assessment. By following a hierarchical ecosystem typology such as the IUCN GET (Figure 5), the different levels of ecosystems represent different ecological equivalencies.

Figure 5. The IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology (global-ecosystems.org) indicating the six hierarchical levels from global to local scales (from: <https://global-ecosystems.org/page/typology>)

This is particularly material in the context of corporate biodiversity target setting (e.g. NNL / net-gain / net-positive commitments) and performance monitoring over time, with immediate financial implications as one changes from one typology to another (e.g. increases / decreases in offset liabilities). For example, let's look at selecting between IUCN GET levels 2 or 5 (**Figure 5** and **Table 4**):

- ▶ First, the biome-level approach (**Figure 6**, top) fails to identify freshwater ecosystems. In the worst-case scenario, this typology may falsely suggest that expanding operations within the study area poses no threat to freshwater ecosystems. In the best-case scenario, even if a company acknowledges impacts on wetlands, all terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem effects are combined into a single ecosystem account, distorting ecological reality. This may lead to stakeholder challenges and unexpected costs in the future.
- ▶ Second, attaining NNL for a single ecosystem type (e.g., Northern Pacific Taiga, in the biome-level classification) is considerably easier than for three distinct types (e.g., Boreal Forest, Mountain Tundra, and wetlands, in the national-level classification, **Figure 6**, bottom). A finer-grained delineation of ecosystems facilitates mitigation planning to be better aligned with site-specific constraints, notably the applicable compliance environment.

Figure 6. The same 15 000 ha study area delineated by biome-level ecosystems (top) and the finer national-level ecosystems (bottom).

In this hypothetical case study, while overall net changes are the same for the two classification systems (-2000 Ha eq.) (Table 4), lower classification systems (IUCN GET level 5: Ecosystem types) provide finer-scale understanding of changes in the state of ecosystems. Indeed, three distinct ecosystem types are tracked. As expected, there are large net losses for Polar Tundra forests (1916.67 ha eq.) and for Polar Tundra grasslands (166.67 ha eq.). But there is also a net gain of 83.33 ha eq. for Polar Tundra wetlands. This provides a more nuanced picture than what the “IUCN GET level 2: Biome” net change assessment provides.

Table 4. Net changes from a 1990 baseline different ecosystem typology classification levels

Ecosystem type	State score	1990 baseline		2020		2025		1990-2025	
		TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	Net change (ha)	Net change (ha eq.)
IUCN GET LEVEL 2									
T6.3 Polar Tundra	5	10000.00	8333.33	7000.00	5833.33	5000.00	4166.67	-5000.00	-4166.67
T6.3 Polar Tundra	4	2500.00	1666.67	5000.00	3333.33	4000.00	2666.67	1500.00	1000.00
T6.3 Polar Tundra	2	2500.00	833.33	3000.00	1000.00	6000.00	2000.00	3500.00	1166.67
Totals		15000.00	10833.33	15000.00	10166.67	15000.00	8833.33	0.00	-2000.00
IUCN GET LEVEL 5									
Polar Tundra forests	5	8000.00	6666.67	5000.00	4166.67	3500.00	2916.67	-4500.00	-1916.67
Polar Tundra forests	4	0.00	0.00	2500.00	1666.67	1000.00	666.67	1000.00	
Polar Tundra forests	2	2500.00	833.33	3000.00	1000.00	6000.00	2000.00	3500.00	
Polar Tundra grasslands	5	1000.00	833.33	750.00	625.00	0.00	0.00	-1000.00	-166.67
Polar Tundra grasslands	4	1250.00	833.33	1500.00	1000.00	2250.00	1500.00	1000.00	
Polar Tundra wetlands	5	1000.00	833.33	1250.00	1041.67	1500.00	1250.00	500.00	83.33
Polar Tundra wetlands	4	1250.00	833.33	1000.00	666.67	750.00	500.00	-500.00	
Totals		15000.00	10833.33	15000.00	10166.67	15000.00	8833.33	0.00	-2000.00

2.6 Reference state determination

Four foundational concepts shape how we measure ecosystem states over time (McNellie *et al.* 2020) (Figure 7):

- ▶ **Reference states** offer an ecological context for evaluating the state of species, populations, habitats, ecosystems, or biodiversity as a whole. These states can be established using proxies, surrogates, or indicators, and may apply at both site-specific and broader landscape scales. These can refer to different time scales, from pre-human times, pre-industrialization times to present-day best on offer benchmarks (Figure 7). These time-specific reference states should be preferred over value-laden terms such as *healthy, natural, pristine* or *wild*.
- ▶ **Benchmarks** provide quantitative parameters that help define reference states. These may be determined through empirical data or expert judgment and may include various metrics or composite indicators.
- ▶ **Baselines** introduce the starting point from which we start measuring changes in ecosystem state (Mihoub *et al.* 2017). Baselines are used to compare ecosystem states over a given period, typically to track changes against targets. They are arbitrary in nature as they reflect policy, management or business decisions. Reference states ensure that all baselines are comparable.
- ▶ **Targets** provide the objectives we may strive to reach in terms of ecosystem state. These are typically broken down into subsidiary targets for each step of the mitigation hierarchy. For instance, restoration measures may have a specific ecosystem state as a target while offset measures may seek properties with ecosystems falling within a specific range of ecosystem state (e.g. anything above a threshold indicating high biodiversity value).

Figure 7. A conceptual framework for synthesizing the historical and contemporary reference states and their context and applications within the context of informing corporate biodiversity footprints; adapted from (Bedford *et al.* 2023; McNellie *et al.* 2020)

Determining which ecosystem state to use as a reference poses a significant challenge for biodiversity footprinting. The diversity of goals and the variability in timeframes complicate the selection of a reference state, leading to criticism of the concept as being overly complex and difficult to validate (McNellie *et al.* 2020):

- ▶ Reference states may become impractical targets when based on distant, variable, and often vague historical periods (Suding 2011). This may be due to the fragmented and often ambiguous nature of historical, archaeological, and palaeoecological evidence, making expert-derived reference states challenging to substantiate.
- ▶ Historical reference states are potentially unsuitable for present and future ecological contexts because of the extent of changes in environmental or climatic conditions that have shaped them (Hobbs *et al.* 2014). See Section 2.2 for further discussion of anthropogenic influences on ecosystems through time.
- ▶ The reliance on benchmarks are frequently derived from heuristic methods such as expert judgement or opinion (Faber-Langendoen *et al.* 2012; Gibbons *et al.* 2008). Yet, expert opinions carry inherent assumptions about ecological processes, disturbance regimes, resiliency and/or irreversibility of changes as they reflect diverse historical, social, political, economic, and cultural biases (Burgman *et al.* 2011; Kahneman 2013).

Reflecting on these limitations, one may argue for the concept of the contemporary reference state (Figure 7) grounded in contemporary biodiversity value-based reference states as opposed to traditional disturbance-driven historical baselines (McNellie *et al.* 2020). For instance, the 'Best-of-What's-Left' concept (Stoddard *et al.* 2006) or the 'Best-on-Offer' reference state (Eyre *et al.* 2006) focus on known, extant states characterised by high levels of current biodiversity values within and among contemporary ecosystems. This perspective is often expressed by many companies that realise that it is impossible for many ecosystems to ever reach those historical reference states (pers. obs.).

Yet, choosing the reference has significant impacts on ecosystem state assessment (see Section 3.7 for an illustration). Using present day benchmarks would typically lead to overestimated ecosystem state measurements, failing to recognise historical losses. While there is no one-size fits all solution, clearly recording the choices made, along with their assumptions, limitations and benefits, should provide the required level of confidence for the purpose of corporate biodiversity footprint assessment. The key pitfall to avoid is environmental amnesia, ensuring that what's 'Best-of-What's-Left' or 'Best-on-Offer' considers all key ecosystem variables (Section 2.6) and extirpated species (i.e. adjusting benchmark score below the maximum value), which could be candidate for reintroduction.

Dracaena cinnabari, The dragon blood tree. (VU)

UNDERSTANDING DATA QUALITY FOR DECISION MAKING: A CASE STUDY

Key Messages

1. A **real-world case study from Queensland**, Australia shows that differences in typology, spatial scale, measurement methods, and reference states lead to substantially different ecosystem state assessments.
2. Ecosystem typologies shape estimates of ecosystem gains and losses. Only pre 1750 Regional Ecosystems provide a consistent basis for biodiversity footprint accounting, because **anthropogenic categories lack meaningful reference states** and typology changes can mask historical losses and complicate long-term comparisons.
3. The **spatial scale of ecological equivalency** determines what can and cannot be compared. Coarse typologies obscure important ecological differences across the landscape.
4. **Measurement methods produce divergent outcomes**. MSA and BII generalize conditions using pressure–state models, which flatten ecological variation. EVI measures vegetation greenness, not ecosystem state, and is therefore inappropriate for ecosystem state assessment. Field based ecosystem data remain essential but are difficult to scale across landscapes.
5. Reference state selection has a major influence on results. Using present day benchmarks such as “Best on Offer” tends to overestimate ecosystem state relative to historical reference states. **Historical baselines better capture long term degradation** and help avoid environmental amnesia.
6. **Transparent documentation of all assumptions is essential** for credible biodiversity footprinting and corporate target setting. Our Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) process integrates high resolution satellite imagery, secondary spatial datasets, and expert ecological interpretation to generate spatially explicit ecosystem state scores and confidence levels.

3.1 Methodological approach

To illustrate the real-world implications of the challenges discussed in Section 2, we have put together a case-study from a location with publicly available, high-quality data of ecosystem state. The case study is not intended to validate a single set of ‘correct’ ecosystem state results, but to demonstrate how methodological choices systematically shape outcomes. We are comparing different ecosystem typologies at different levels of granularity and different state measurement metrics.

To situate the case study within the broader landscape of corporate biodiversity assessment practice, we used two globally prominent pressure - state biodiversity indices: Mean Species Abundance (MSA) and the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII). Both indices are widely used in global biodiversity modelling, biodiversity footprint assessments, and risk-screening applications.

In contrast, we also used local, site-based information: the regulatory BioCondition data available for part of the study area provide direct, field-based measurements of ecosystem structure, composition, and function relative to contemporary benchmark reference states. While these data offer high ecological validity at the site scale, their point-based nature and limited spatial coverage constrain their applicability for biodiversity footprinting across larger landscapes or value chains.

To bridge the gap between coarse, pressure-based biodiversity indices and spatially limited site-based surveys, this case study applies a structured Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA), which integrates high-resolution satellite imagery, secondary spatial datasets, and expert ecological interpretation to produce spatially explicit ecosystem state scores and associated confidence levels across the wider landscape (see **Figure 8**; full methodology in Annex C). We provide the output data for all typologies in Annex A and the complete MESA biodiversity footprint accounts, as per the BD Protocol, as Annex D.

Figure 8. Conceptual overview of the Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) as applied in the case study. Full details available in Annex C.

3.2 Study area

This case study draws on publicly available data from a land-based biodiversity offset established under Australia's Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999 (EPBC Act) for impacts to the *Lowland Rainforest of Subtropical Australia* Threatened Ecological Community (TEC). An offset site located at Kawana (Sunshine Coast Region, Queensland) (**Figure 9**) was legally secured in 2020 and managed to improve biodiversity state through weed control, regeneration, and revegetation actions over a defined management timeframe (GHD 2020). Baseline assessments were undertaken in 2020 using the Queensland BioCondition framework, with subsequent monitoring designed to track changes relative to benchmark reference states and defined performance criteria.

We used the site location and available monitoring data in ArcGIS Pro Version 3.6.1 and Q GIS Version. 3.42.3 to illustrate the ramifications of different decisions on ecosystem state measurement. We focused on the Kawana offset area (27.76 ha) near Brisbane and expanded it by drawing a 2.5 km buffer from the centre point to produce a case study area of 1962.46 ha (**Figure 9**). The area covers both natural remnant vegetation, agricultural areas, an urban centre, natural watercourses and artificial canals.

Figure 9. Location of case study area situated on the Sunshine Coast of Queensland, Australia. We selected an offset with publicly available data and created a 2.5 km buffer to create a case study area covering both natural and modified systems.

3.3 Comparing ecosystem and land use typologies

This case study applies the conceptual distinction introduced earlier in the paper (Section 2.2) between ecosystem typologies that reflect original, pre-industrial ecosystems and those that incorporate anthropogenic systems. The objective is to demonstrate how the inclusion or exclusion of anthropogenic systems directly influences ecosystem state measurement outcomes.

Queensland provides an unusually strong empirical context for this analysis due to the availability of detailed, spatially explicit ecosystem mapping (Neldner *et al.* 2019). Regional Ecosystem (RE) datasets include both inferred pre-1750 ecosystem distributions, representing native vegetation patterns prior to widespread European land clearing, and contemporary vegetation datasets that classify land as remnant or non-remnant based on its departure from those historical ecosystems. Non-remnant categories typically aggregate a wide range of anthropogenic land uses, including urban areas, agriculture, plantations, and heavily modified or regrowth vegetation.

First, **Table 5** shows the extent of the different ecosystem categories for each typology. Tracking changes in the state of ecosystems would thus generate vastly different results depending on the selected typology. While only the pre-1750 one deals exclusively with ecosystem types (e.g. changing an ecosystem type from one category to another requires ecological evidence) (**Figure 10**, panels C and E), the land use classification is particularly problematic because it reflects land use planning decisions rather than ecology (**Figure 11**, panels A and B).

Furthermore, **Figures 10** and **11** contrast the three typological approaches across the case study region and the Kawana offset site. When contemporary typologies incorporating anthropogenic systems are used, large portions of the landscape are classified as non-remnant vegetation without a clearly defined reference state against which ecosystem state can be assessed (**Figure 10**, panels D and F). In such cases, ecosystem state measurement becomes ambiguous, as there is no agreed reference for the expected structure, composition, or functioning of these systems in the context of biodiversity conservation.

Consistent with the methodological position advanced in this paper, we should conduct ecosystem state measurement using the pre-1750 Regional Ecosystem typology. Under this approach, all areas within the study boundary are treated as instances of original ecosystem types that have experienced varying degrees of transformation, rather than as distinct anthropogenic systems. Areas currently occupied by agriculture, urban development, or artificial infrastructure are retained spatially in the analysis, but are interpreted as fully transformed states of their original ecosystems, rather than as ecosystem assets in their own right.

Table 5. Extent of ecosystems or Total Biodiversity Footprint (TBF) for the study area according to different regional typologies. For full ecosystem names see Annex B. Ecosystems are ordered in descending area.

	Ecosystem name	Total area (TBF) (ha)		Ecosystem name	Total area (TBF) (ha)		Ecosystem name	Total area (TBF) (ha)
Pre 1750 Regional ecosystems	12.3.5	1021.43	Remnant Regional Ecosystems	Non-remnant	1191.42	Land use	Nature	744.64
	12.2.7	285.92		12.3.5	380.38		Urban	662.31
	12.2.12	156.21		Water (dams)	107.43		Agriculture	555.51
	12.3.11/12.3.5	106.32		12.3.1a	41.92		Total	1962.47
	12.9-10.14	99.69		12.3.6	41.79			
	12.3.1a	70.09		12.3.1a/12.3.5	39.29			
	12.3.1a/12.3.5	66.23		12.3.13	32.80			
	12.3.6	41.79		12.2.7	31.97			
	12.3.13	41.09		12.9-10.14	19.49			
	12.1.1	19.91		Canal	18.14			
	12.3.2	19.71		12.1.1	17.39			
	Estuary	17.33		Estuary	17.34			
	12.9-10.4	7.36		12.3.2	16.34			
	12.1.3	6.28		12.1.3	6.28			
	12.3.11	1.66		12.2.12	0.50			
	12.2.15	1.44		Total	1962.47			
	Total	1962.47						

Figure 10. Comparison of two ecosystem typologies across the 2.5km buffer case-study region (top) and offset site (bottom) comparing the historical Pre 1750 Regional Ecosystems (left) and a typology which includes modified anthropogenic systems (Remnant Regional Ecosystems). Compare to **Figure 11** of the land use typology.

Figure 11. Comparison of two ecosystem typologies across the case- study region (left) and offset site (right) using a landuse typology to compare to **Figure 10**.

3.4 Equivalency at different spatial scales

This case study illustrates how the recognition of ecological equivalency at different spatial scales has a material influence on ecosystem state measurement outcomes and their interpretation for biodiversity footprinting. As discussed earlier in the paper (Section 2.5), ecological equivalency rules influence how ecosystem losses and gains can be meaningfully compared, aggregated, or offset. It is therefore central to both regulatory compliance and voluntary corporate biodiversity commitments.

Ecosystem typologies provide the primary mechanism through which ecological equivalency is operationalised. Using the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology as a conceptual reference, ecosystem classifications can be applied at progressively finer hierarchical levels, from coarse bioregional or biome-level groupings to detailed regional ecosystem types. Each level implies a different degree of ecological equivalence, with direct consequences for biodiversity footprinting.

Figure 12 and **Table 6** demonstrate this effect for the case study area. At the coarsest scale (Bioregion; Panel A), the landscape is represented as a single Ecosystem Type (ET). At intermediate scales, such as broad vegetation groups (panel B), there is still substantial loss of ecological heterogeneity with 11 ETs. At the level

of regional ecosystem groupings (panel C), some differentiation is restored leading to 16 ETs. However, important distinctions remain unresolved, particularly between terrestrial, freshwater, and estuarine systems. Only at finer typological resolutions, where ecosystem types are delineated by both vegetation characteristics and realm (panel D), do ecologically distinct systems become visible as separate accounting units.

This distinction is particularly material in the context of biodiversity footprinting and target-setting. From an accounting perspective, each ecosystem type represents a distinct asset, and losses or gains must be assessed independently for each asset to avoid inappropriate substitution.

For instance, the Kawana offset was designated under Australia's *Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act* as compensating for impacts to the *Lowland Rainforest of Subtropical Australia* Threatened Ecological Community. While the offset area covers 27.76 ha in total, only 15.21 ha correspond to the specific regional ecosystem type (RE 12.3.1a) for which equivalency is required; the remaining area comprises other, non-equivalent ecosystem types that should not be aggregated for biodiversity footprinting and accounting purposes.

This case study further demonstrates that typological resolution has direct implications for reported biodiversity outcomes. At coarse classification levels, net gains and losses may appear balanced or even positive when aggregated across broad ecosystem groupings. At finer resolutions however, gains in some ecosystem types may coexist with persistent losses in others, revealing residual biodiversity liabilities that would otherwise remain hidden.

Table 6.

Ecosystem typology and extent at classification scales

Typology	Ecosystem name	TBF (ha)	Typology	Ecosystem name	TBF (ha)
A. Bioregion	South eastern Queensland	1962.47	D. Realm and Pre 1750 Regional Ecosystems	Terrestrial 12.3.5	934.86
	B. Broad vegetation groups	22a		1349.13	Terrestrial 12.2.7
29a		197.30		Terrestrial 12.2.12	155.21
4b		136.33		Terrestrial 12.3.11/12.3.5	101.05
16c		107.97		Terrestrial 12.9-10.14	99.69
8b		99.69		Freshwater 12.3.5	86.25
28a		19.91		Terrestrial 12.3.1a	48.32
8a		19.71		Freshwater 12.3.1a/12.3.5	46.65
Estuary		17.33		Terrestrial 12.3.13	39.08
9g		7.36		Terrestrial 12.3.6	35.04
35a		6.28		Freshwater 12.3.1a	21.78
34c		1.44		Freshwater 12.1.1	19.88
Total		1962.47		Terrestrial 12.3.2	19.71
C. Pre 1750 Regional Ecosystems		12.3.5		1021.43	Terrestrial 12.3.1a/12.3.5
	12.2.7	285.92		Freshwater estuary	17.33
	12.2.12	156.21		Freshwater 12.2.7	16.18
	12.3.11/12.3.5	106.32		Terrestrial 12.9-10.4	7.36
	12.9-10.14	99.69		Freshwater 12.3.6	6.75
	12.3.1a	70.09		Freshwater 12.1.3	6.28
	12.3.1a/12.3.5	66.23		Freshwater 12.3.11/12.3.5	5.27
	12.3.6	41.79	Freshwater 12.3.13	2.01	
	12.3.13	41.09	Terrestrial 12.2.15	1.44	
	12.1.1	19.91	Freshwater 12.2.12	1.01	
	12.3.2	19.71	Freshwater 12.3.11	0.91	
	Estuary	17.33	Terrestrial 12.3.11	0.74	
	12.9-10.4	7.36	Freshwater 12.3.5	0.32	
	12.1.3	6.28	Terrestrial 12.1.1	0.03	
	12.3.11	1.66	Total	1962.47	
	12.2.15	1.44			
	Total	1962.47			

Figure 12. Comparison of different levels of ecosystem typology for the case study area going from a coarse bioregion (A), broad vegetation groups (B) to regional ecosystems (C) which are further subdivided into realms (D).

3.5 Different measurement approaches generate very distinct ecosystem states

To illustrate how methodological choices affect ecosystem state measurement, the case study compares commonly used data types: modelled pressure–state indices, remotely sensed vegetation indicators, and primary field-based ecosystem state data. **Table 7** compares the four approaches as per the criteria defined by Bedford *et al.* (2022): spatial precision, measurement accuracy, responsiveness of measurement to mitigation measures and feasibility at scale.

Figure 13 presents two widely applied modelled biodiversity indices - Mean Species Abundance (MSA) (Alkemade *et al.* 2009), the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) (Newbold *et al.* 2016) - alongside the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), a remotely sensed indicator of vegetation greenness (Huete *et al.* 2002) and the manual classification of site-based imagery (MESA) as per the scoring system presented in Annex C.

MSA and BII estimate biodiversity state indirectly by modelling relationships between human pressures and species abundance relative to a reference state. These are produced at regional to global scales. As such, they are well suited to biodiversity risk screening and broad prioritisation.

For site-level ecosystem state measurement however, these indices have important limitations. Their coarse spatial resolution, fixed or temporally aggregated reference periods, and reliance on inferred pressure–state relationships limit their ability to detect local variation or short-term change in specific ecosystems.

EVI, by contrast, is available at finer spatial and temporal resolution and captures vegetation dynamics across the landscape. In the case study, it clearly distinguishes forested areas from agricultural and urban land uses and reflects temporal variability in vegetation productivity. However, EVI measures greenness rather than ecological integrity. Intensively managed or irrigated systems may exhibit high EVI values despite low biodiversity and simplified ecosystem structure. EVI therefore cannot be interpreted as a proxy for ecosystem state without additional ecological information.

Site-based data remain essential for high-confidence ecosystem state measurement, but their limited availability across large areas means they cannot meet all biodiversity footprinting needs. Importantly, the absence of field data does not justify defaulting to coarse, pressure-based indices or global averages that mask local ecological states. Instead, there is a clear role for intermediate approaches that combine remotely sensed data, secondary spatial information, and ecological expertise to assess ecosystem state in a transparent and spatially explicit way (i.e. MESA – see Annex C). Our manual ecosystem state assessment applied here bridges this gap, providing ecologically meaningful, decision-useful estimates of ecosystem state where site-based monitoring is not feasible, with confidence levels explicitly reflecting data availability.

Overall ecosystem state results are presented in **Figure 14**. While EVI and MSA scores over-estimate ecosystem states, BII and MESA scores are closer to each other. However, there are only four spatial units for BII. MESA, with its 471 units, does provide a more accurate picture of the ecological reality.

Figure 13. Comparison of two common ecosystem state indices across the case-study area: The Mean Species Abundance (A), and the Biodiversity Intactness Index (B) against a time series of a vegetation greenness indicator, the Enhanced Vegetation Index (C, D) and the manual ecosystem state assessment (E, F). Dates are indicative of the source data acquisition.

Table 7. The characteristics of the different methodologies applied in the case study, classified as low, medium, or high as defined by [Bedford *et al.* \(2022\)](#)

Methodology characteristic	MSA (Mean Species Abundance – GLOBIO)	BII (Biodiversity Intactness Index – NHM)	EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index)	Manual assessment of site-based imagery (MESA)
Spatial precision of state measurement	Medium – Biodiversity state represented at broad spatial scales (e.g. ecoregion, pressure grid); not site-specific.	Medium – Spatially explicit gridded outputs but represents average biodiversity state across broad areas rather than specific sites.		High – State assessed at the specific site or footprint boundary represented in the imagery.
Accuracy of measurement	Low – Estimates state change based on modelled pressures and global response curves rather than direct observation of on-the-ground state.	Low – Reflects empirically derived biodiversity responses, but changes are modelled and not ground-truthed at individual sites.	Not a measure of ecosystem state but an index of greenness.	Medium to High – Reflects observable on-the-ground features; accuracy depends on expert judgement and imagery quality, but not fully ground-truthed unless paired with field data.
Responsiveness of measurement to mitigation	Low – Metric responds primarily to changes in pressure inputs (e.g. land-use class), not to site-level mitigation actions or management quality.	Low – Not responsive to site-level mitigation; changes only occur when underlying land-use or pressure layers change.		High – Can respond directly to site-level mitigation actions (restoration, rehabilitation, avoidance) at appropriate temporal scales.
Feasibility to apply at scale	High – Highly scalable; can be applied rapidly across portfolios and regions without site-specific data.	High – Designed for national to global application; scalable across countries and reporting cycles.		Medium – Able to be applied rapidly at scale but requires location data. Can adapt in-situ data already collected for other purposes if available.

Figure 14. Overall state of ecosystems for the study area for each measurement approach comparing the Total Biodiversity Footprint (TBF), Positive Biodiversity Footprint (PBF), Negative Biodiversity Footprint (NBF) and Number of spatial units (discrete polygons or pixels)

3.6 Navigating through ecosystem complexity

In this case study, ecosystem complexity is addressed through the combined use of site-based ecological surveys and spatially explicit state assessment across the wider landscape. Measuring ecosystem complexity through structural, compositional, and functional metrics via on-the-ground surveys is well established.

For the offset site, primary ecosystem site data is publicly available and were collected through on-the-ground surveys undertaken by a suitably qualified ecologist in 2020 (baseline), 2022, and 2024 (Figure 16) (WSP 2022, 2024) Monitoring was conducted using the BioCondition Framework (Eyre. *et al.* 2015) which assessed a defined set of indicators capturing vegetation composition, structure, and key functional attributes within permanent 100 m × 50 m transects (Figure 15). These included native species richness across growth forms, canopy structure and recruitment, ground cover composition, coarse woody debris, litter, and indicators of disturbance, supported by photographic records and species verification through the Queensland Herbarium. These data provide direct, site-specific measurements of ecological state against current regional ecosystem benchmarks for the Lowland Rainforest Threatened Ecological Community.

Figure 15. Location of two transects with three sampling points each in the Kawana offset site. Locations extracted from [WSP \(2022\)](#).

Table 4.1 Kawana site condition results

Assessment unit – regional ecosystem	Kawana RE 12.3.1A								
Site reference	Benchmark	KBC1			KBC2			Average% benchmark	Score
Kawana offset site condition	12.3.1a	Raw data	% Benchmark	Score	Raw data	% Benchmark	Score		
Recruitment of woody perennial species in EDL	100	90	90%	5	90	90%	5	90%	5
Native plant species richness – trees	11	23	209%	5	21	191%	5	200%	5
Native plant species richness – shrubs	17	22	129%	5	23	135%	5	132%	5
Native plant species richness – grasses	1	1	100%	5	1	100%	5	100%	5
Native plant species richness – forbs	16	18	113%	5	19	119%	5	116%	5
Tree Height Canopy	28	30	107%	5	30	107%	5	107%	5
Tree Height Sub-canopy	8	8	100%		10	125%		113%	
Tree Cover Canopy	80	73	91%	5	96	120%	5	106	5
Tree Cover Sub-canopy*	40	N/A (60, in 2022)	N/A (150%, in 2022)		N/A (71, in 2022)	N/A (178%, in 2022)		N/A (163% in 2022)	
Shrub canopy cover	28	20.5	73%	5	77	275%	3	174%	4
Native perennial grass cover	1	0	0%	0	0	0%	0	0%	0
Organic litter	30	97	323%	3	99.8	333%	3	328%	3
Large trees (euc plus non-euc)	150	156	104%	15	114	76%	10	90%	12.5
Coarse woody debris	295	135	46%	3	115	39%	3	42%	3
Non-native plant cover	0	0	0%	10	0	0%	10	0%	10
Site Condition Score				71			64		67.5
Maximum Site Condition Score				80			80		80
Site Condition Score – out of 7				6.21			5.60		5.91

*Tree sub-canopy cover was counted with the canopy cover during the 2024 survey. Therefore, 2022 scoring has been applied for sub-canopy cover (in brackets) to provide an indicative score. In addition, the benchmark for sub-canopy cover was previously erroneously reported in 2022 (Table 4.1) to be 28 rather than 40.

Figure 16. Extract from project document reporting BioCondition scores for the Kawana offset site for 2024 (from WSP, 2024 pp. 14)

The BioCondition scores were supplemented by a site context score (Figure 17) that captured landscape-scale attributes such as patch size, connectivity, and surrounding land use. The scale is 0-3 with 3 being the benchmark value. The BioCondition score and site context score were then combined in accordance with Queensland assessment guidelines to produce an overall habitat quality score, representing both the intrinsic ecological state of the site and its functional value within the broader landscape; with a benchmark value of 10.

Site context	KBC1	Score	KBC2	Score	Average KBC1 / KBC2	Average score
Size of patch (ha)	181	7	181	7	181	7
Connectedness	90	5	90	5	90	5
Context	37	4	37	4	37	4
Ecological Corridors	Within	6	Within	6	–	6
Role of site location to TEC overall population in the state	Yes	5	Yes	5	–	5
Threats to the species	Low	15	Low	15	–	15
Site Context Score	–	42		42	–	42
<i>MAX Site Context Score</i>	–	46		46	–	46
Site Context Score – out of 3	–	2.74		2.74	–	2.74

Final habitat quality score (weighted)	KBC1	KBC2	Average / final
Site Condition score (out of 7)	6.21	5.60	5.91
Site Context Score (out of 3)	2.74	2.74	2.74
Habitat Quality score (out of 10)	8.95	8.34	8.65
Assessment Unit area (ha)	181	181	181.00
Total offset area (ha) for this MNES	181	181	181.00
Size Weighting	1.00	1.00	1.00
Weighted Habitat Quality Score out of maximum of 10	8.95	8.34	8.65

Figure 17. Extract from project document reporting site context scores and overall habitat quality scores for the Kawana offset site for 2024 (from WSP, 2024 pp. 15)

The field-based BioCondition data were directly used to characterise ecosystem state within the offset site and to anchor ecosystem state scoring in the manual assessment. However, these data are not area-bound in a way that supports direct translation into homogeneous ecosystem state polygons for biodiversity footprint accounting purposes. Field-based methodologies are well established for assessing ecosystem structure, composition, and function relative to reference states, but are inherently limited by their point-based nature, which constrains inference about the spatial extent of state, and by their high resource intensity, which restricts coverage across large areas.

This is why we developed our manual ecosystem assessment approach to provide a consistent and transparent means of estimating ecosystem state across large areas, to bridge the gap between large-scale, but inaccurate indices and where field-based monitoring would be impractical or resource-prohibitive. The assessment integrates high-resolution satellite imagery, available secondary spatial datasets (e.g. vegetation mapping, land-use information, disturbance layers), and expert ecological judgement to evaluate ecosystem composition, structure, and function relative to defined reference states.

Using the methodology and broad terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem state scoring systems in Annex C, polygons of homogenous state were scored from 0 (fully transformed) to 6 (historical reference state). The results are presented for 2020 and 2024 (**Figure 18**), along with the change in state, and a confidence map. The confidence map indicates higher confidence for fully transformed polygons and where site-based data is

available (offset area). The remainder of the remnant vegetation scores ‘fair confidence’ where visual assessment of satellite imagery was the only available data source.

Figure 18. Results of the manual ecosystem state assessment combining field data (for the offset site) and expert scoring of satellite imagery for 2020 and 2024, and the change between the years. Confidence in assessment (same for both years) reflects clear transformation and where site-based data is available. For full methodology see Annex C.

3.7 Reference state determination

The selection of a reference state has practical and material implications for ecosystem state measurement and the interpretation of biodiversity outcomes. This is illustrated here using the primary ecosystem state data available for the Kawana offset site.

As reported in **Figure 17**, the overall habitat quality score for each transect is derived from the combination of a BioCondition site condition score (maximum = 7) and a site context score (maximum = 3), yielding a benchmark reference value of 10. In accordance with the Queensland BioCondition framework, these reference values are calibrated against contemporary benchmark sites and therefore represent a present-day reference state, often described as a “best-on-offer” (Eyre. *et al.* 2015).

While appropriate for regulatory monitoring and compliance purposes, present-day benchmarks do not represent an unmodified historical reference state. In eastern Australia, substantial ecosystem degradation and species loss has occurred since European settlement, particularly for rainforest ecosystems, many of which are now listed as threatened ecological communities. As a result, contemporary benchmark sites are likely to reflect residual biodiversity values rather than historical ecosystem states, a consequence of the shifting baseline syndrome (see sections 2.2 and 2.6) (Soga & Gaston 2018)

To illustrate the implications of this distinction, we apply an additional reference state adjustment to the Kawana offset data to represent a hypothetical historical reference state. This adjustment is *not intended as a prescriptive correction*, but rather as a sensitivity analysis designed to demonstrate how reference state selection influences ecosystem state metrics. Specifically, we increased the reference values by a nominal value of 1.0 as the minimum discrete increment consistent with the integer-based scoring framework, representing a conservative assumption about the degree to which contemporary benchmarks underestimate historical ecosystem states. Thus the BioCondition site condition benchmark is increased from 7 to 8, the site context benchmark is increased from 3 to 4, resulting in an overall historical reference value of 12. This adjustment reflects the likely loss of compositional and functional attributes at the ecosystem level that are not captured by present-day benchmarks, including extirpated species and altered ecological processes.

Using this adjusted reference state, state-adjusted surface area values (ha eq.) for the offset site are systematically lower than those calculated using present-day benchmarks (**Figure 19**). For the Kawana offset, ecosystem state estimates based on present-day reference values are 16.6 % higher in 2020 and 22.5 % higher in 2024 compared to estimates derived using the historical reference state (**Table 8**). These differences arise solely from reference state selection, not from changes in measured ecosystem state.

This example highlights the risk of environmental amnesia when present-day benchmarks are used uncritically in biodiversity footprint assessments (**Figure 20**). While historical reference states may be difficult to reconstruct with precision, failing to account for long-term ecosystem degradation can lead to overestimation of ecosystem state and potentially misleading interpretations of biodiversity performance. For corporate biodiversity footprinting, transparency regarding reference state choice - including its assumptions, limitations, and implications - is therefore essential for decision-usefulness and credibility.

Table 8. The differences in ecosystem state metrics for different reference states for the individual polygons within the offset site using the data provided.

Eco-system	Area (ha)	Habitat quality score		Reference values		State-adjusted surface area = (area x ecosystem state score / reference value)			
		2020	2024	Present-day benchmark	Historical	2020		2024	
						Present-day benchmark	Historical	Present-day benchmark	Historical
12.3.5	9.16	7.68	8.34	10	12	7.03	5.87	8.00	6.65
12.3.2	3.38	7.68	8.95	10	12	2.60	2.16	2.87	2.39
12.3.1a	15.21	7.68	8.95	10	12	11.69	9.74	13.15	10.97

Figure 19. The difference in ecosystem state scores, given as condition-adjusted surface area metric (ha eq.) when using field data against a present-day reference benchmark and a historic reference benchmark.

Figure 20. Comparison of biodiversity footprint metrics between 2020 and 2024 using the present-day benchmark and historic reference states for the offset site.

4

CONCLUSIONS

This paper demonstrates that measuring ecosystem state is both essential and inherently complex. As businesses face rising disclosure expectations and biodiversity-related risks, ecosystem state offers a practical and scalable proxy for understanding broader biodiversity trends. Yet, as shown throughout the document, conceptual ambiguity, inconsistent terminology, and fragmented policy responses create significant challenges for companies attempting to assess, monitor, or report on their impacts. A structured and transparent approach to ecosystem state measurement is therefore critical for aligning private-sector action with global biodiversity goals.

We show that methodological choices - ranging from the selection of ecosystem typologies and spatial scales to the use of different measurement approaches and reference states - materially shape assessment outcomes. Coarse typologies mask ecological variation, pressure-based models overlook on-the-ground realities, and present-day benchmarks risk embedding environmental amnesia. Conversely, finer-scale classifications, direct ecological indicators, and transparent reference frameworks provide more ecologically robust and decision-useful results but are incredibly difficult to scale up. The case study from Queensland illustrates how these methodological decisions systematically influence the magnitude and distribution of ecosystem gains and losses.

Effective biodiversity-related decision-making depends not on using more data, but on making explicit, decision-aligned choices about ecosystem typologies, spatial scale, reference states, and acceptable levels of uncertainty. Looking forward, credible biodiversity footprinting requires methodological transparency, ecological consistency, and explicit recognition of uncertainty. No single approach can meet all needs, but combining various data sources and expert knowledge can help quantify it. Our structured Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) process offers a practical pathway for generating reliable ecosystem state information across landscapes and value chains. By adopting rigorous and well-documented methods, businesses can generate assessments that are comparable, defensible, and aligned with the deeper objective of reversing biodiversity loss.

Accounting (biodiversity)

Accounting (biodiversity): Biodiversity accounting for organisations can be defined as the systematic process of identifying, measuring, recording, summarising and reporting the biophysical state of biodiversity assets and the periodic and accumulated net changes to those assets (BD Protocol).

Biodiversity accounting must follow accounting rules:

1. An asset inventory or register of affected ecosystems and material species, organized in line with relevant international (e.g. IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology) and national classification systems (e.g. EUNIS Habitat Classification in Europe, South African ecosystem types, Terrestrial Ecological Systems of the United States),
2. Measurement techniques that use spatially explicit data, suitable to each asset category,
3. The assessment of net impacts for gains and losses of like-for-like assets (ecological equivalency principle) in line with the mitigation hierarchy,
4. Use of recording rules based on double-entry bookkeeping from financial accounting,
5. Compilation of asset-specific statements of performance and position, which can be aggregated for ecosystems but need to be kept separate for material species,
6. Time period assumption (i.e. time can be divided into distinct and consecutive periods and that accounting transactions can be allocated to these periods using criteria laid out by other rules and principles), and
7. The segregation of biodiversity state data per value chain boundary, as well as per type of impact (direct, indirect, future).

(Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020)

Baseline (impact assessment)

A minimum or starting point with which to compare other information (e.g. for comparisons between past and present or before and after an intervention). As it results from a decision, a baseline is dependent on a business and / or legal context. It is arbitrary in nature. It is different from a reference state.

(Bedford *et al.* 2023)

Biodiversity footprint assessment boundary

The combination of your selected organisational and value chain boundaries makes up your company's biodiversity impact inventory boundary. These impacts may be direct, indirect and / or cumulative, sometimes extending beyond the legal boundaries of your operations (e.g., downstream impacts due to wastewater incidents).

Biodiversity impact (or impact on biodiversity)

The negative or positive effect of business activity on biodiversity. The BD Protocol defines a biodiversity impact (or impact on biodiversity) as a change in the state of biodiversity.

This change can be positive or negative, or both, for instance a positive change for an ecosystem (e.g. increase in structural complexity of a forest as trees age and die) may be negative for a species (e.g., decrease in the population size of a herb shaded under a closed canopy) within the same spatial area.

Biodiversity footprint (Total Biodiversity Footprint, Positive Biodiversity Footprint, Negative Biodiversity Footprint)

A biodiversity footprint refers to the total impact of an organisation, project, region, service or product on biodiversity and is one option to assess impacts. More specifically, for the BD Protocol, a Biodiversity Footprint is the sum of positive and negative impacts of an organisation on biodiversity over a given organisational and value chain boundary.

The BD Protocol specifies that the Total Biodiversity Footprint (TBF) is made of a Positive Biodiversity Footprint (PBF) and a Negative Biodiversity Footprint (NBF).

For ecosystems:

- ▶ The TBF is the sum of the surface areas of ecosystems within the assessment boundary,
- ▶ The PBF is the surface area adjusted for state (i.e. hectares equivalents) of ecosystems within the assessment boundary,
- ▶ The NBF is the difference between the TBF and PBF, also expressed in surface area adjusted for state / integrity.

For species:

- ▶ The TBF is the Target population / habitat size within impact inventory (i.e. direct impacts of direct operations). It is different from the viable minimum population size.
- ▶ The PBF is the current population / habitat size.
- ▶ The NBF is the difference or gap between its current population / habitat size and the target / ideal population / habitat size (as determined by science and business context).
(Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020; Houdet & Teren 2022)

Biological Diversity Protocol (BD Protocol)

The BD Protocol is the first standardised accounting framework that enables any organisation to identify, measure, record, compile and disclose its biodiversity impacts. The BD Protocol focuses on impacts on ecosystems and material species. Genetic diversity is excluded at this stage.

(Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020)

State-adjusted surface area

A standard measurement framework for ecosystems, combining physical area or volume with a measure of its state compared to the intact state (or reference state). They may be expressed as quality-hectares or weighted hectares. 'Extent × Condition' is the framework adopted by the UN for ecosystem accounting and is widely used in corporate biodiversity assessments.

(United Nations et al. 2021)

Ecological Equivalency

It reflects the concept of 'like-for-like' when measuring the different components or aspects of biodiversity. When considering gains and losses and/ or developing a biodiversity account, one cannot net off changes in the state of one species or ecosystem with that of another. That is, only the same types of ecosystems or species can be compared within a net impact assessment.

Ecosystem state

Ecosystem state simply describes where an ecosystem stands, at a given place and time, against its reference situation. It describes shifts in ecosystem state that can occur both positively and negatively, and as a result of human activities and/or natural drivers.

Target (ecosystem state)

Targets provide the objectives we may strive to reach in terms of ecosystem state. These are typically broken down into subsidiary targets for each step of the mitigation hierarchy.

Ecosystem typology

Ecosystem typologies provide the primary mechanism through which ecological equivalency is operationalised. Using a hierarchical ecosystem typology, the different levels of ecosystems represent different ecological equivalencies. The selection of an appropriate ecosystem typology directly shapes the results of an assessment.

Environmental amnesia

Environmental amnesia refers to the phenomenon whereby each generation perceives the environmental conditions of its formative years as normative, thereby overlooking long-term ecological degradation. This cognitive bias contributes to a diminished awareness of historical ecosystem states, masking the full scope of transformation that has occurred throughout the Anthropocene.

Impact driver

Impact drivers are exerted by business activities (e.g., pollution from emissions or land conversion by agriculture) and result in a change (positive or negative) in the state of biodiversity. These impacts in turn have consequences (positive or negative) for business and society.

Impact drivers are also called 'pressures' in the Drivers, Pressures, State, Impact, Responses (DPSIR) framework advocated by the Science-Based Targets Network (SBTN) and 'direct drivers of change' under the Convention for Biological Diversity (CBD) and IPBES. Indirect drivers of change, such as the broader underlying causes of the direct drivers like population change and technological innovation (also called 'Drivers' in the DPSIR framework), cannot be directly attributed to, or managed by, a company. An impact driver generally has three main characteristics: magnitude (e.g., amount of contaminant, noise intensity), spatial extent of the impact driver (e.g., area of land changed) and temporal extent (e.g. duration of persistence of contaminant). Impact drivers may result in both positive and negative changes in the state of biodiversity and associated impacts on business or society (e.g., impacts on human wellbeing). Several impact drivers, either from one company or combined with those of other organizations, can result in cumulative impacts.

(Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020; Natural Capital Coalition 2016)

Land use

The human use of a specific area for a certain purpose (such as residential, agriculture, recreation, industrial, etc.). Influenced by, but not synonymous with, land cover. Land use change refers to a change in the use or management of land by humans, which may lead to a change in land cover.

Mitigation Hierarchy

The hierarchy refers to the sequence of actions taken to:

- ▶ Anticipate and avoid impacts on biodiversity;
- ▶ Minimise or reduce impacts where avoidance is not possible;
- ▶ Rehabilitate or restore when impacts have occurred; and
- ▶ Compensate or offset significant residual impacts.

This concept is widely used throughout the world and is often embedded into national legislation as regards to environmental permitting

1. First: Avoidance measures to avoid generating impacts from the outset, such as careful spatial or temporal placement of elements of infrastructure, in order to avoid impacts on natural capital as much as possible.
For example: Locating a project outside a Key Biodiversity Area.
2. Second: Minimisation measures to reduce duration, intensity and/or extent of impacts that cannot be completely avoided, as far as practically feasible.
For example: Minimising the spread of material and waste flows, scheduling of vegetation clearing at the appropriate time.
3. Third: Restoration / rehabilitation measures to assist recovery of an ecosystem type that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed by business activities.
For example: Rehabilitation of a mining site or quarry.
4. As a last resort: Offset measures to compensate for any residual significant, adverse impacts on natural capital that cannot be avoided, minimised and/or rehabilitated or restored, often implemented in order to achieve no-net-loss, or a net gain, of biodiversity. This may be achieved outside the immediate project area, through active biodiversity restoration or creation projects, or through averted risk/loss offsets which aim to prevent likely future risks of harm to (or losses of) biodiversity from occurring. The latter option requires the definition of an appropriate counterfactual, in other words determining what would have happened without the offset. Examples of averted-loss offsets include the expansion of a protected area network in areas under pressure from third parties.
5. Above and beyond: Additional conservation measures may also be undertaken. These refer to voluntary pro-biodiversity measures that may be undertaken by companies. These are not linked to the company's residual impacts on biodiversity but may play an important role in its biodiversity strategy.

(BBOP 2018; Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP) 2012)

Net impact

The net result of equivalent biodiversity gains and losses over a period. Core to the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy, it requires an assessment of the baseline or existing conditions to provide a starting point (e.g. pre-project state of biodiversity) against which comparisons can be made (e.g. post-impact state of biodiversity), allowing changes in biodiversity to be measured throughout the project or business life-cycle.

Offset measures, aimed at reaching no-net-loss or net gains, have been applied to a growing number of projects worldwide (e.g. property development, linear infrastructures, mines), typically in the context of project authorisation processes.

Pressure–state model

Model-based assessments estimate biodiversity change by quantifying the effects of specific pressures and establish pressure–state relationships, often calibrated using global datasets. These indices estimate biodiversity state indirectly by modelling relationships between human pressures and species abundance relative to a reference state.

Realm

Major components of the living, natural world that differ fundamentally in ecosystem organisation and function: terrestrial (land), freshwater, marine (ocean), subterranean and atmospheric (IUCN GET).

Transformed

Changes made to an area by human activity, such as urban development, agriculture, or infrastructure expansion. This term encompasses alterations in land cover and land use, often impacting the environment and ecosystems.

(IPBES 2018)

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COMPANY PROFILE

Our Vision

To be the **reference** in biodiversity footprinting by providing **transparent, evidence-backed, and actionable insights** that help businesses move beyond greenwashing into real, measurable impact. We envision a future where **biodiversity accounting is as rigorous as financial reporting**, equipping organizations with the tools to navigate complexity, set meaningful targets, and take credible action for nature.

Our Mission

We cut through the noise, demystifying biodiversity measurement and strategy with **deep insight and scientific integrity**. Our work empowers corporations, municipalities, financial institutions, and policymakers with the **clarity and confidence** to make informed, responsible decisions that align with ecological reality.

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Annex A: Ecosystem state scores in 2020 and 2024 for different ecosystem typologies using MESA

	ET Name	2020				2024			
		TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	NBF (ha eq.)	PBF: TBF (%)	TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	NBF (ha eq.)	PBF: TBF (%)
Broad vegetation groups	29a	197.30	23.56	173.75	12.00	197.3	23.56	173.75	12.00
	35a	6.28	3.67	2.62	58.00	6.28	3.67	2.62	58.00
	9g	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00
	4b	136.33	57.04	79.29	42.00	136.33	57.04	79.29	42.00
	34c	1.44	0.03	1.41	2.00	1.44	0.03	1.41	2.00
	8a	19.71	4.67	15.05	24.00	19.71	4.67	15.05	24.00
	28a	19.91	11.34	8.57	57.00	19.91	11.34	8.57	57.00
	16c	107.97	18.16	89.82	17.00	107.97	18.16	89.82	17.00
	22a	1349.13	382.68	966.45	28.00	1349.13	383.31	965.83	28.00
	8b	99.69	16.45	83.24	17.00	99.69	16.02	83.67	16.00
	Estuary	17.33	8.19	9.15	47.00	17.33	8.19	9.15	47.00
	Total	1962.47	525.78	1436.69	27.00	1962.47	525.97	1436.50	27.00
Regional Ecosystem	Estuary	17.33	8.19	9.15	47.24	17.33	8.19	9.15	47.24
	12.3.13	41.09	21.05	20.04	51.23	41.09	21.05	20.04	51.23
	12.1.1	19.91	11.34	8.57	56.97	19.91	11.34	8.57	56.97
	12.9-10.4	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00
	12.1.3	6.28	3.67	2.62	58.33	6.28	3.67	2.62	58.33
	12.3.6	41.79	24.38	17.41	58.33	41.79	24.38	17.41	58.33
	12.3.11	1.66	0.28	1.38	16.67	1.66	0.28	1.38	16.67
	12.2.15	1.44	0.03	1.41	2.02	1.44	0.03	1.41	2.02
	12.2.12	156.21	2.51	153.71	1.61	156.21	2.51	153.71	1.61
	12.3.11/12.3.5	106.32	17.88	88.44	16.82	106.32	17.88	88.44	16.82
	12.2.7	285.92	16.85	269.06	5.89	285.92	15.92	270	5.57
	12.3.1a/12.3.5	66.23	29.46	36.78	44.47	66.23	29.46	36.78	44.48
	12.3.1a	70.09	27.58	42.51	39.35	70.09	27.58	42.51	39.35
	12.3.5	1021.43	341.45	679.98	33.43	1021.43	343.01	678.42	33.58
	12.9-10.14	99.69	16.45	83.24	16.50	99.69	16.02	83.67	16.07
	12.3.2	19.71	4.67	15.05	58.33	19.71	4.67	15.05	58.33

	ET Name	2020				2024			
		TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	NBF (ha eq.)	PBF: TBF (%)	TBF (ha)	PBF (ha eq.)	NBF (ha eq.)	PBF: TBF (%)
	Total	1962.47	525.78	1436.69	27.14	1962.47	525.97	1436.5	27.15
Realm and Regional Ecosystem	Terrestrial 12.3.13	39.08	19.88	19.20	50.86	39.08	19.88	19.2	50.86
	Terrestrial 12.1.1	0.03	0.02	0.01	58.33	0.03	0.02	0.01	58.33
	Terrestrial 12.9-10.4	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00	7.36	0.00
	Terrestrial 12.3.6	35.04	20.44	14.6	58.33	35.04	20.44	14.6	58.33
	Terrestrial 12.3.11	0.74	0.12	0.62	16.67	0.74	0.12	0.62	16.67
	Terrestrial 12.2.15	1.44	0.03	1.41	2.02	1.44	0.03	1.41	2.02
	Terrestrial 12.2.12	155.21	2.32	152.89	1.49	155.21	2.32	152.89	1.49
	Terrestrial 12.3.11/12.3.5	101.05	16.98	84.07	16.81	101.05	16.98	84.07	16.81
	Terrestrial 12.2.7	269.74	12.13	257.61	4.50	269.74	11.19	258.55	4.15
	Terrestrial 12.3.1a/12.3.5	19.59	5.78	13.81	29.50	19.59	5.78	13.81	29.5
	Terrestrial 12.3.1a	48.32	19.93	28.38	41.25	48.32	19.93	28.38	41.25
	Terrestrial 12.3.5	934.86	301.97	632.89	32.30	934.86	303.53	631.33	32.47
	Terrestrial 12.9-10.14	99.69	16.45	83.24	16.50	99.69	16.02	83.67	16.07
	Terrestrial 12.3.2	19.71	4.67	15.05	23.67	19.71	4.67	15.05	23.67
	Freshwater estuary	17.33	8.19	9.15	47.24	17.33	8.19	9.15	47.24
	Freshwater 12.3.13	2.01	1.17	0.84	58.33	2.01	1.17	0.84	58.33
	Freshwater 12.1.1	19.88	11.33	8.56	56.97	19.88	11.33	8.56	56.97
	Freshwater 12.1.3	6.28	3.67	2.62	58.33	6.28	3.67	2.62	58.33
	Freshwater 12.3.6	6.75	3.94	2.81	58.33	6.75	3.94	2.81	58.33
	Freshwater 12.3.11	0.91	0.15	0.76	16.67	0.91	0.15	0.76	16.67
	Freshwater 12.2.12	1.01	0.19	0.82	18.82	1.01	0.19	0.82	18.82
	Freshwater 12.3.11/12.3.5	5.27	0.90	4.37	17.05	5.27	0.90	4.37	17.05
	Freshwater 12.2.7	16.18	4.73	11.45	29.21	16.18	4.73	11.45	29.21
	Freshwater 12.3.1a/12.3.5	46.65	23.68	22.97	50.76	46.65	23.68	22.97	50.76
	Freshwater 12.3.1a	21.78	7.65	14.13	35.13	21.78	7.65	14.13	35.13
	Freshwater 12.3.5	86.57	39.48	47.09	45.61	86.57	39.48	47.09	45.61
	Total	1962.47	525.78	1436.69	26.79	1962.47	525.97	1436.5	26.80

Annex B. Descriptions of Ecosystem Types used in the assessment

Broad Vegetation group codes	Short Description
4b	Evergreen to semi-deciduous mesophyll to notophyll vine forests, frequently with <i>Archontophoenix</i> spp., fringing streams
8a	Wet tall open forests dominated by species such as <i>Eucalyptus grandis</i> (flooded gum) or <i>E. saligna</i> , <i>E. resinifera</i> (red mahogany), <i>Lophostemon confertus</i> (brush box), <i>Syncarpia</i> spp. (turpentine), <i>E. laevopinea</i> (silvertop stringybark)
8b	Moist open forests to tall open forests mostly dominated by <i>Eucalyptus pilularis</i> (blackbutt) on coastal sands, sub-coastal sandstones and basalt ranges. Also includes tall open forests dominated by <i>E. montivaga</i> , <i>E. obliqua</i> (messmate stringybark), and <i>E. campanulata</i> (New England ash)
9g	Moist to dry woodlands to open forests dominated by stringybarks or mahoganies such as <i>Eucalyptus tindaliae</i> (Queensland white stringybark), <i>E. latisinensis</i> (white mahogany), <i>E. acmenoides</i> (narrow-leaved white stringybark); or <i>E. racemosa</i> (scribbly gum) or <i>E. seeana</i> or <i>E. tereticornis</i> (blue gum) and <i>Corymbia intermedia</i> (pink bloodwood)
16c	Woodlands and open woodlands dominated by <i>Eucalyptus coolabah</i> (coolibah) or <i>E. microtheca</i> (coolibah) or <i>E. largiflorens</i> (black box) or <i>E. tereticornis</i> (blue gum) or <i>E. chlorophylla</i> on floodplains. Does not include alluvial areas dominated by herblands or grasslands or alluvial plains that are not flooded
22a	Open forests and woodlands dominated by <i>Melaleuca quinquenervia</i> (swamp paperbark) in seasonally inundated lowland coastal areas and swamps
28a	Complex of open shrublands to closed shrublands, grasslands, low woodlands and open forests, on strand and foredunes. Includes pure stands of <i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i> (coastal she-oak)
29a	Open heaths and dwarf open heaths on coastal dunefields, sandplains and headlands
34c	Palustrine wetlands. Freshwater swamps on coastal floodplains dominated by sedges and grasses such as <i>Oryza</i> spp., <i>Eleocharis</i> spp. (spikerush) or <i>Baloskion</i> spp. (cord rush) / <i>Leptocarpus tenax</i> / <i>Gahnia sieberiana</i> (sword grass) / <i>Lepironia</i> spp. Includes small areas of estuarine wetlands
35a	Open heaths and dwarf open heaths on coastal dunefields, sandplains and headlands

Pre-1750 Regional Ecosystem codes	They can be broken down into terrestrial, freshwater and marine realms.
12.1.1	<i>Casuarina glauca</i> woodland on margins of marine clay plains
12.1.3	Mangrove shrubland to low closed forest on marine clay plains and estuaries
12.2.7	<i>Melaleuca quinquenervia</i> or rarely <i>M. dealbata</i> open forest on sand plains
12.3.1a	Gallery rainforest (notophyll vine forest) on alluvial plains
12.3.2	<i>Eucalyptus grandis</i> tall open forest on alluvial plains
12.3.5	<i>Melaleuca quinquenervia</i> open forest on coastal alluvium
12.3.6	<i>Melaleuca quinquenervia</i> +/- <i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i> , <i>Lophostemon suaveolens</i> , <i>Corymbia intermedia</i> open forest on coastal alluvial plains
12.3.11	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i> +/- <i>Eucalyptus siderophloia</i> , <i>Corymbia intermedia</i> open forest on alluvial plains usually near coast
12.2.12	Closed heath on seasonally waterlogged sand plains
12.3.13	Closed heathland on seasonally waterlogged alluvial plains usually near coast
12.2.15	<i>Gahnia sieberiana</i> , <i>Empodisma minus</i> , <i>Gleichenia</i> spp. closed sedgeland in coastal swamps
12.9-10.14	<i>Eucalyptus pilularis</i> tall open forest on sedimentary rocks
12.9-10.4	<i>Eucalyptus racemosa</i> subsp. <i>racemosa</i> woodland on sedimentary rocks
Estuary	Naturally occurring estuary

Annex C: Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA)

- See separate document.

Annex D: Full biodiversity accounts for the manual assessment of the case study.

- See separate excel.